

Channel Modeling using Deep Neural Network with RIS-powered
Wireless Communication Systems
From 5G to 6G

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Deep Neural Network with RIS

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Outline: Introduction, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces

- Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces provide an improvement of performance of wireless communications.
- By utilizing software-controlled meta-surfaces for the reflected signals from the source to destination.
- especially when the direct path is weak and hence improving the antenna array.
- Analytical tools: QuadriGa, MATLAB

Introduction continued

- Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS) technology is a promising way for the improvement of the performance of wireless communication systems.
- The RIS is a two-dimensional surface built on the usage of electromagnetic meta-materials.
- Such surfaces have a potential for the capacity improvement and coverage extension as a result of partial control of propagation environment.
- One should note that for a MIMO channel with no RIS, the throughput is determined by the channel matrix $y=Hx$.
- Each element determines signal gain α & β , the phase shifts to the RIS elements.
- With beyond 5G, the advent of electromagnetic components that can shape how they interact with wireless signals enables partial control of the propagation.

Preliminaries

- An RIS is a thin surface composed of N elements, each being a small antenna that receives and passively re-radiates with a configurable time delay.
- For narrowband signals, this delay corresponds to a phase shift, are properly adjusted.
- The scattered waves add constructively at the receiver, resembles traditional beamforming.
- each element has a fixed radiation pattern, but the collection of phase shifts determines where constructive interference among the scattered waves occurs.
- LIS, generating and reflecting electromagnetic waves, while RIS is only used to reflect electromagnetic waves.
- For machine learning simulations, RIS has been replaced by LIS.

Preliminaries continued

$$y = (R\Phi T + H)x + n$$

- where $x = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{N_t}]^T$. The noise is $n \approx \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$
- It belongs to $\mathbb{C}^{N_t \times 1}$ for the T_x signal, and y is the R_x signal.
- The matrix \mathcal{H} corresponds to the direct connection between T_x and R_x .
- R is the channel coefficient and the phase shifting, representing the diagonal RIS reflection matrix.
- This describes the incident signal amplification and phase shift of the each UC.
- RIS induces some phase between the reflected signals and make them interfere either between the reflected signals and make them interfere constructively implying the desired signal strength increases at the receiver or destructively to mitigate the co-channel interference.

More Preliminaries, Phase Shift

$$\Phi = \text{diag}(\alpha_1 e^{j\beta_1}, \dots, \alpha_M e^{j\beta_M})$$

- phase shifting is written as above representing the diagonal RIS reflection matrix.
- where each element determines the signal gain of α . The β represent corresponding phase shifts to the UCs.
- For a MIMO channel with no RIS, the throughput is determined by the channel matrix $y = Hx$

Channel modeling, Machine Learning

- LOS and NLOS estimation with scenarios, e.g. UMi (urban microcell), RIS moving with respect to SNR & capacity versus rate used.
- When one is looking beyond 5G, the advent of electromagnetic components that can shape how they interact with wireless signals¹.
- This enables partial control of the propagation of a channel.
- One should note that a reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS) is a two-dimensional surface of engineered material with properties not static.
- Input variables: Number of Users, Number of transmit Antennas and Receiving antennas
- Number of RIS elements. In general 30 or 40.
- The downlink bandwidth > 30 GHz, and Rayleigh fading

¹Burtakov2023.

RIS Simulation

- The model is stationary, and is unsupervised, could be changed to supervised.
- The Optimizer is designed in Matlab with deep learning using convolutional and deep neural network.
- Number of data symbols as input and the reflection matrix has $\beta = \{0, 1\}$

(a) RIS-aided Wireless Communication System

(b) Wi-Fi network with RIS

(c) flowchart DNN

Figure: RIS-simulations

- In Figure 1b, RIS position x_{RIS} varied, RIS configured with ON-OFF algorithm.
- SNR are measured for COS-UC, Q-UC and CST-UC.
- Powers $P_{T_x} = 30$, dBm, and $P_N = -85$, dBm, noise power. $M = \{256, 400\}$, Operating frequency 5.3 GHz.
- Figure 1c and Figure 2b provide an idea of the DNN implementation.
- For the validation of CST-UC behaviour, a comparison of free-space scenarios was done by using QRIS with CST-UC and full-wave simulation in CST.
- Done by modeling half-wave antenna in CST and imported into QRIS, QuadriGa to make the transmitter and receiver behaviour same in both cases.

- The P_{R_x} , the receiving power is calculated as below in Watts for figure 2a.
- This is calculated without RIS impact using the Friis equation for free-space propagation.

$$P_{R_x} = \frac{\lambda^2 P_{T_x} G_{T_x}(\phi_d, \theta_d) G_{R_x}(\phi_a, \theta_a)}{(4\pi)^2 d_{TR}^2}$$

Neural Network with RIS continued

- where λ is the wavelength.
- P_{T_x} , the transmitting power.
- G_{T_x} , and G_{R_x} are:
- The radiation patterns of transmitter and receiver respectively.
- The (ϕ_d, θ_d) and (ϕ_a, θ_a) , the angle of departure and angle of arrival.
- Eventually one can use Neural network and RIS both to calculate the receiving power.
- Furthermore, the main advantage of QuadRiGa is that it offers predefined channel models with parameters calibrated according to 3GPP standard channel model.
- One can study the different simulation scenarios both for sub-6GHz and mm-Wave ranges.

Rates and Neural Network

(a) Achievable Rate versus distance

Neural network for the input: Transmit antenna, receive antenna, number of elements of RIS, SNR and diagonal matrix's data selection.

The second figure shows the combination of all the outputs.

(b) Neural network

Simulations using DNN

- Training the network we create different scenarios by using different number of RIS elements.
- With different number of transmit and receive antennas with different number of users.²
- The physical environment is modeled such that the directions are uniform randomly drawn from the interval $[\rho_i, \pi]$.
- The coefficient β in the diagonal matrix is chosen with permittivity approximately equal to zero.
- The table depicts the simulation results in the next slide.

²Elbir2020.

Simulation results with DNN and RIS

Table: Root mean square (RMSE) and DNN performance

Epoch	Iteration	Time Elapsed	Mini-batch1	Validation1	Mini-batch2	Validation2	Base learning
1	1	04	142.27	137.37	10120.57	9435.50	$2.1e^{-6}$
4	50	53	55	57.43	1513.89	1655.40	$2.1e^{-6}$
7	100	43	23.30	27.40	271.30	373.80	$2.1e^{-6}$

Conclusion & Future work

- A comparison shown by using different software(s) with RIS, showing the effectiveness of using RIS when the direct link may be partially blocked.
- Further, a DNN approach is implemented between the RIS elements and R_x for the actual prediction on EE, OP and BER.
- Please see Figure 2(b) and table in the previous slide.
- Furthermore, one may use by integrating QRIS with network simulator ns-3 to enable system level analyses of wireless networks.
- Our main softwares are QuadriGa and MATLAB.